

Results of “Scaling and depth variability of source parameters in central and southern Italy using regional attenuation models” by D. Bindi, D. Spallarossa, M. Picozzi, G. Tarchini, submitted to Bulletin of Seismological Society of America, special issue on “ Improving Measurements of Earthquake Source Parameters”

The archive contains:

REPO

- | - **GITout** --> [Results of the spectral decomposition](#)
- | | - model_atte_T2.csv --> spectral attenuation for T2
- | | - model_atte_N1.csv --> spectral attenuation for N1
- | | - model_atte_N2.csv --> spectral attenuation for N2
- | | - model_atte_GA.csv --> spectral attenuation for GA
- | | - model_atte_AQ.csv --> spectral attenuation for AQ
- | | - model_atte_CA.csv --> spectral attenuation for CA
- | | - model_atte_N3.csv --> spectral attenuation for N3
- | | - model_atte_T1.csv --> spectral attenuation for T1
- | | - model_atte_N4.csv --> spectral attenuation for N4
- | | - model_atte_AM.csv --> spectral attenuation for AM
- | | - model_atte_AD.csv --> spectral attenuation for AD
- | | - model_atte_ALL.csv --> spectral attenuation no polygon
- | | - site_amp.csv --> site amplifications
- | | - source_git.csv --> source spectra
- | | - plot_source_spectra.R --> R script to plot sources
- | | - plot_attenuation.R --> R script to plot attenuation
- | | - plot_site_amp.R --> R script to plot site amp
- | | - GITsource_spectra.jpg --> figure sources
- | | - GITsite_amp.jpg --> figure site amp
- | | - GITattenuation.jpg --> figure attenuations
- | - **TABLEparam** --> [Tables with final source parameters](#)
- | | - table_parameters_git_reg.csv --> with polygons
- | | - table_parameters_git_NOreg.csv --> without polygons
- | | - plot_parameters.R --> R script to compare results
- | | - figure_parameters.jpg --> figure with comparison
- | - **REGRE** [Random effects \(RE\) of models in equations 7 and 8](#)
- | | - model_eq7_random_effects.csv
- | | - model_eq8_random_effects.csv
- | | - model_eq8_random_effects_nested.csv
- | - **INFO** [Information about events and stations](#)
- | | - stations.csv
- | | - events.csv

Columns of the source parameter tables:

ID: event ID (YYMMGGhhmmss)

EvLat,EvLon,EvtDpt: latitude, longitude and depth of event

mldb: local magnitude

ROI: polygon including the event location
mo,dmo: \log_{10} of the seismic moment and its error
mw,semw: moment magnitude and its error
fc,dfc: corner frequency [Hz] and its error
vcovD: covariance between M_0 and fc from the source fit
errfit: error of the source fit with Brune model
df: degrees of the freedom of the source fit
vs3D: shear wave velocity used to compute the stress drop
drop_vs_3D,sestdr: stress drop [MPa] and its error.